

A check list of the family Coccinellidae (Latr., 1807), in Entomological collection of Institute of Zoology

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Abstract:

The article provides information about the species of hard-winged insects belonging to the family Coccinellidae (Latr., 1807) in the collection of entomology of the Institute of Zoology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their distribution areas.

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Introduction

Representatives of the family Coccinellidae (Latr., 1807) are widespread on earth. In the Palearctic region, 2,000 species of members of this family are distributed. Many species belong to the lady beetle, which lives alone in agroecosystems. Recent molecular morphological studies have also suggested that coccinellidae (Coccinellidae) be divided into 9 subfamilies and 42 tribes [Nedved and Kovar, 2012; 1-12-p.].

Coccinellidae family
Coccinellinae subfamily
Coccinellini tribe
Coccinella

Coccinella Linnaeus, 1758 category

Coccinella undecimpunctata (Linnaeus, 1758) type.

Area of collection and number of specimens. Kashkadarya region Abrora (44 pieces), Jizzakh (2 pieces), Kara-Kum (2 pieces), Tashkent (2 pieces), Samarkand (1 piece), Kyzylkum (1 piece), Bukhara (1 piece), Yangi Obod (2 pieces), Ertoshsoy (1 piece), Khumson (1 piece).

Collection time: 23.05.1968, 02.07.1979, 22.04.1953, 15.10.1972, 15.05.1968, 07.06.1974, 1958, 04.01.1993, 10.02.1995, 06.06.1995.

Synonyms:

Distribution: It is a widespread species in Europe, Asia, North Africa, the CIS and Uzbekistan.

Ecology: Although this species is widespread, it is widespread mainly in open forest areas, in the deserts and steppes as xerophiles of agricultural areas.

Coccinella septempunctata

Area of collection and number of specimens. Shakhrisabz of Kashkadarya region (2 pieces), Abrora of Kashkadarya region (2 pieces), Nishan district of Kashkadarya region (2 pieces), Tashkent region (1 piece), Jizzakh region (1 piece), Ertoshsay (1 piece), Andijan (1 piece), Surxondaryo (3 pieces).

Collection time: 13.05.1968, 20.06.1967, 09.10.1964, 09.07.1968, 02.07.1979, 07.02.1994, 27.04.1961, 17.05.1973.

Distribution: Widespread in the Palearctic and Nearctic. It is found in Asia, in all regions of the CIS, everywhere in Uzbekistan.

Coccinulla generation of time.

Coccinula sinuatomarginata Faldermann, 1837

Area of collection and number of specimens Kamashi district of Kashkadarya region (1 piece), Jizzakh (30 pieces), Khumson (2 pieces), Shafirkan district of Bukhara region (12 pieces), Yangiabad (5 pieces), Red sand (1 piece), Angren (4 pieces), Kashkadarya Karshi region (1 piece).

Collection time:

Synonyms:

Coccinula quatuordecimpustulata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Area of collection and number of specimens Tashkent region New Road (1 piece), Ertoshsay (2 pieces), Karabakh (1 piece), Jigaristan (2 pieces).

Distribution: This species is common in the Palearctic. Occurs in Europe, Asia, North Africa, CIS, deserts of Uzbekistan, forest edges, gardens, sparse forests and foothills.

Coccinula redimita(Linnaeus, 1758) type.

Area of collection and number of specimens. Ertoshsay (1 piece), Tashkent (2 pieces), Jizzakh region Bakhmal (3 pieces), Kashkadarya region Karshi (1 piece).

Collection time:20.06.1996, 04.06.1978, 13.07.1976, 27.05.1968.

Distribution:

Propylaea Mulsant, 1846 category.

Propylaea quatuordecimpunctata (Linnaeus, 1758) type.

The collection has been paid for and the number of samples. Tashkent region, Yertoshsay, Jigaristan. 1953, 1952, 1996, 1995, 1994.

Distribution:

The most common type of transparent art is found in Europe, Asia, Africa, CIS and Uzbekistan.

Ecology: It is a mesophilic species, found mainly in trees in spring and early summer, and then migrates to melons and field crops and feeds on plant lice.

Adalia Mulsant, 1846 category.

Adalia decempunctata (Linnaeus, 1758) type.

Area of collection and number of specimens. Khumson, Tashkent, Institute of Botany, Karabakh, Yertoshsay, Angren, Kamashi, 1995, 1975, 1972, 1980, 1968, 1969, 1993, 1970,

Distribution: It is a common species in the Palearctic. Widespread in Western Europe, North Africa, Japan, CIS-Europe, Siberia, Central Asian republics and Kazakhstan. Rare in desert and semi-desert areas.

Ecology: Occurs in a variety of herbaceous plants and fruit trees. The beetles overwinter under the apricot peel.

Stethorus Weise, 1885 category.

Stethorus punctillum (Weise, 1891) type.

Area of collection and number of specimens. Tashkent, Arnasay, Khumson, Karabakh, 1928, 1929, 1925, 1966, 1979, 1997, 1996

Distribution: A common species in the Palearctic. Occurs everywhere in Western Europe, North America, the CIS-Europe, the Caucasus, Siberia, Ukraine, Central Asia, Uzbekistan.

Ecology It is found in fruit trees, crop fields, and wild plants around them, and beetles and juveniles feed on the eggs, larvae, and larvae of spiders.

***Nephus quadrimaculatus* (Herbst, 1783) type .**

Area of collection and number of specimens Jizzakh, Yangi-obod, Angren, Chetsuv, Ertoshsoy, 1984, 1995, 1993.

Distribution: Occurs in the southern part of the Palearctic. It is more common in Western Europe, Siberia, the Caucasus, Central Asia, the European part of the CIS, Tashkent and Syrdarya and Surkhandarya regions of Uzbekistan.

Ecology: In the foothills, steppes and irrigated lands, cotton, hemp and cannabis are found in arable lands and feed on plant lice.

Fabr, 1787. Mantissa Insect.60 (*Coccinella*)

Type: *quadrivulneratus* Mulsant, 1850

***Scymnus frontalis* (Fabricius, 1787) type.**

Area of collection and number of specimens. Tashkent, Kashkadarya, New Road, Karshi, Andijan, Fergana, Khumson, Zaamin, Kyzyl-Kum, Bukhara, Surkhandarya, Bakhmal, Sari-Chelak, Ertoshsay, Naugarzon, Karabakh, Chetsuv, 1929,1968,1953,1965, 1970,1962, 1969, 1952, 1961, 1951, 1970, 1974, 1975, 1973, 1979, 1997.

Distribution: Palearctic tour. It met in Western Europe, Siberia, Mongolia, former Asia, the European part of the CIS-Carpathians, the Caucasus, Irkutsk, Yakutia, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan.

Ecology: Widespread in foothills. Perennials, acacias, and fruit trees feed on plant lice.

***Scymnus rubromaculatus* (Goeze, 1777) type.**

Area of collection and number of specimens. Kashkadarya, Khumson, Bakhmal, Bukhara, Zaamin, Turkestan, 1968, 1969, 1974, 1976, 1975, 1967, 1976.

Distribution: Southwest Palearctic Tour. Occurs in Western Europe, Siberia, Mongolia, Central Asia, the European part of the CIS, Ukraine, Uzbekistan, Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya.

Ecology: Mesophilic species, common on river banks, in the lower part of the mountain range. Beetles and larvae feed on mites, nettles, reeds, sorghum, alfalfa, and alfalfa and vegetable lice. Occasionally there is a protein-rich diet in vegetables.

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